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Research Article

**THALASSEMIA IN MICROCYTIC HYPOCHROMIC ANEMIA
PATIENTS**¹Noor-ul-Huda, ²Musfra Maham, ²Dr. Mussarat Sharif¹Sir Ganga Ram Hospital²Allied Hospital Faisalabad**Abstract:**

Objective: The purpose of this study is to assess the regularity of α -gene, β -gene, and hemoglobin different facts in patients with Microcytic hypochromic anemia.

Methodology: 340 patients (out of 850) with microcytic hypochromic anemia [MCV<80fl; MCH<27pg] were study in Mayo Hospital Lahore. This study includes a total of 325 individuals out of which 88 patients were of Alpha-thalassemia trait, 171 patients of Beta-thalassemia trait, 42 with iron-deficiency anemia, 13 with thalassemia major and 11 with hemoglobin variants (HbS, HbC, and HbD). Remaining 15 out of 340 patients not diagnosed with any certain etiology.

Results: With gap-PCR, Genotyping for $-\alpha^{3.7}$, $-\alpha^{4.2}$, $-\alpha^{PA}$, $-\alpha^{5NT}$ and $- -^{MED}$ was done. The overall ratio of deletion of $-\alpha^{3.7}$ is 20% in 325 individuals. 23 most acknowledge β -gene mutations Genotyping completed through absolute transformation investigation thru Amplification Refractory Mutation System (ARMS). The most recurrent transformations were CD 36/37, IVS I-110 and IVS II-I in 340 patients with 9.7%, 3.5% and 11.7% respected rates. Statistically noteworthy dissimilarity exist among Beta-thalassemia Major and Beta-thalassemia trait in case of MCH (P-value =0.23) and MCV (p-value = 0.25) indications, and similarly MCH indicator among Hb Variants and Beta-thalassemia trait (P-value = 0.04).

Conclusion: In the province of Punjab α -gene and β -gene alteration is fairly communal. Baffling micro cytosis diagnosed with the help of molecular genotyping of α -thalassemia and β -thalassemia, and resultantly preclude needless iron incrimination.

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INTRODUCTION:

Like many other regional countries, Pakistan has a massive quantity of thalassemia patients [1]. Pakistani people is a combination of various cultural sets, divisions and frequencies of β -globin mutations required elucidation in numerous areas of the country. In Pakistan, with an outstanding frequency of α and β -globin mutation, the improved probability of co-inheritance of α - and β -thalassemia may perhaps consequence in to a huge range of phenotypes [2]. In Pakistan, β -thalassemia is actually erratic however, genetic recurrence of β -thalassemia is more and differs significantly from one area to other. Around the Caspian Sea and Persian Gulf, its peak frequency is over 10%. In contrast to iron deficiency and β -thalassemia trait, α -thalassemia can't be diagnose with simple biochemical test. Data is deficit in Pakistan on α and β genotyping. The preliminary hematological data is Hemoglobin apathies' discovery and categorization, specifically thalassemia. The thalassemia suspicion arises with low MCV (mean corpuscular volume) or MCH (mean corpuscular hemoglobin). Though, low MCV or MCH can result into iron deficiency, it will just indicating the prevalence of thalassemia in that part of country.

Numerous reasons exist for the anemia production from various abnormal hemoglobin's. Generally, hemolytic and dyserythropoietic both are the anemia. In certain, similar to HbS the cause is seeming as oxygen pressure reduction which results in to a course (identified as 'sickling' of red cells) causing them further liable to damage through spleen. The discriminating aspect in anemias because of thalassemia's and iron deficiency are red cell indicators and due to occurrence in the same area, both are extremely essential. In the same way, red cells count increment in thalassemia resulted into less value of MCV and MCH. In hematology clinical practices, microcytic hypochromic anemia is a usual abnormality and generally is because of thalassemia trait and iron deficiency.

In thalassemia's, extensive disparity between MCV ranges shown through the microcytosis degree and mutation type. Narrow information for deletion of α -gene in patients with microcytosis written in literature [3, 4]. Transferors of α -gene deletion have slight microcytosis including or excluding anemia. For identification the basis of microcytosis and to

circumvent recurrent costly investigation or lengthy iron rehabilitation it is significant to identify β -thalassemia even though anemia is discreet or absent. The α -deletions present in patients of β -thalassemia changes the phenotype. No biochemical diagnostic procedure existed for α -thalassemia carriers' findings. Globin chain synthesis studies are costly and laborious, moreover, for investigation it necessitate radioactive amino acids. Molecular techniques, similar to sequencing and Southern blot hybridization, are usually utilize for α -thalassemia's analysis. On the other hand molecular diagnosis through PCR has recognized to be minimum onerous, cheaper and also having more positive results [5, 6]. Amplification Refractory Mutation System (ARMS) is the method used extensively for detection of β -thalassemia' mutation [7, 8]. Dissimilar to β -thalassemia's, common reason of α -thalassemia is deletion. Routinely detected common deletions and rearrangements of α -thalassemia make through gap-PCR [9-11]. Purpose of this study is to identify the thalassemia mutation's prevalence and types of hemoglobin in inexplicable cases of microcytic anemia and its usage in clinical rehearsals.

METHODOLOGY:

Between January 2014 to April 2017, 2ml each (4ml per patient) blood samples in plain and EDTA vials collected from 850 patients at Mayo Hospital Lahore. All patients consented in writing prior to blood collection. i short program of thalassemia, measured the red cell collection on an automatic cell counter (Sysmex Kx-21, Japan) and Hb F and Hb A2 in Hb Variant [Bio-rad USA] system. The TIBC (total iron binding capacity) and serum iron calculated through usage of Span Diagnostics Ltd manufactured kits and accordingly saturation percentage were measure. Patients having <16% iron saturation were counted to be iron-deficient.

After primary assessment, 340 out of 850 collected samples were diagnosed as microcytic (MCV < 80 fl) and hypochromic (MCH < 27 pg mL⁻¹) anemia and included into thalassemia study. Out of these 340 patients, 88 were with Alpha-thalassemia trait 171 with Beta-thalassemia trait. Thalassemia major cases were 13, hemoglobin variants (HbS, HbC, and HbD) were 11, iron-deficiency anemia in 42 cases and 15 patients were found to be with no definite etiology, listed in (Table-I).

Classes	Alpha - genotypes	Numbers (% prevalence)	Homozygote	Heterozygote	Compound heterozygote
1	aa α -a ³⁷	64.0 (72.7)	4.00	60.00	0.00
2	aa ra ^{4.2}	1.0 (1.1)	0.00	1.00	0.00
3	aa α -a ^{FA}	1.0 (1.1)	0.00	1.00	0.00
4	aa α -MED	6.0 (6.8)	0.00	6.00	0.00
5	aa α -a ^{5NT}	3.0 (3.4)	1.00	2.00	0.00
6	HbD and a α -a ^{F2}	1.0 (1.1)	0.00	0.00	1.00
7	HbD and aa α -a ³⁷	1.0 (1.1)	0.00	0.00	1.00
8	HbC and aa α -a ^{3J}	1.0 (1.1)	0.00	0.00	1.00
9	Unknown	10.0 (13.9)	4.00	6.00	0.00
10	Total (% prevalence)	88.0 (100)	9.0 (10.2)	76.0 (86.3)	3.0 (3.5)

Genomic DNA arranged from marginal blood for α and β genotyping through typical phenol chloroform extraction technique. The same protocol as described by Agarwal et al [6] was follow for discovery of α -^{3.7} deletion, α -^{4.2} deletion. Liu et al [12] procedure was follow for other deletion's detection. On 1.5% agarose

gel (Sigma), augmented outcomes were electrophoresing and sullied through ethidium bromide. All 88 α -thalassemia suspected patients were assess via gap-PCR and resultantly found the mutation's type. (Table-II).

Table-II: Hematological parameters in different groups with microcytic hypochromic anemia

Group (No. of cases)	Hb mean	± SD (Range)	MCV mean	± SD (Range)	MCH mean	± SD (Range)
Beta-thalassemia Trait(171)	9.53	1.43	62.90	5.30	20.03	1.80
Beta-thalassemia Major(13)	7.50	1.34	71.60	5.20	22.90	2.10
Iron deficiency(42)	7.75	2.05	69.35	6.95	17.52	2.84
Alpha-thalassemia Trait(88)	11.10	1.25	73.60	4.67	23.90	1.82
Hb Variants(11) *	12.10	2.63	73.90	4.40	23.50	1.65

All 171 suspected β -thalassemia patients were assessed through β -globin gene's direct mutation analysis by ARMS and establish the mutation's type. (Table-III)

Results documented on gel documentation system. SPSS version 11.5 used for statistical analysis and for assessment of hematological parameters a self-governing sample *t* test was used. Allelic frequencies and genotypic were also assessed.

Table-III: Prevalence of 6-thalassemia in various 6-thalassemia subgroups of microcytic hypochromic anemia

Group	Beta - genotypes	Numbers (% prevalence)	Homozygote	Heterozygote	Compound heterozygote
1	CD 36/37	33.0(17.0)	3.00	30.00	0.00
2	IVS II-I	40.0(20.60)	3.00	37.00	0.00
3	6 ^S (CD6 GAG → GTG)	7.0(3.60)	0.00	7.00	0.00
4	HbD ^{Punjab} : 6(CD121 G → C)	3.0(1.50)	0.00	3.00	0.00
5	IVS I-6	5.0(2.50)	5.00	0.00	0.00
6	CD 8(-AA)	7.0(3.60)	1.00	6.00	0.00
7	IVS I - 25	7.0(3.60)	0.00	7.00	0.00
8	- 88 (C → A)	3.0(1.50)	0.00	3.00	0.00
9	CD 8/9	3.0(1.50)	0.00	3.00	0.00
10	IVS I - 110	12.0(6.10)	1.00	11.00	0.00
11	IVS II - 745	7.0(3.60)	0.00	7.00	0.00
12	IVS I - 5	5.0(2.50)	0.00	5.00	0.00

13	CD 83 (-G)	1.0(0.50)	0.00	1.00	0.00
14	CD 44	8.0(4.10)	0.00	8.00	0.00
15	IVS II - 2,3(+11,2)	1.0(0.50)	0.00	1.00	0.00
16	CD 5	3.0(1.50)	0.00	3.00	0.00
17	IVS I - I	3.0(1.50)	0.00	3.00	0.00
18	CD 39	5.0(2.50)	0.00	5.00	0.00
19	IVS I - 130	1.0(0.50)	0.00	1.00	0.00
20	CD44/CD36/37	1.0(0.50)	0.00	0.00	1.00
21	HbC/IVS II - I	1.0(0.50)	0.00	0.00	1.00
22	IVS I - 130/IVS I - 25	1.0(0.50)	0.00	0.00	1.00
23	IVS II - I / IVS II - 745	1.0(0.50)	0.00	0.00	1.00
24	Unknown	36.0(20.80)	10.00	26.00	0.00
25	Total (% prevalence)	194.0(100.00)	23.0(11.80)	167.0(86.00)	4.0(2.20)

RESULTS:

The basic examination of 850 samples of hematological parameters done. In which, 340 samples exhibited hypochromic [MCH < 27 pg] and microcytosis [MCV < 80 fl]. Hemoglobinopathy discovered in 283, iron-deficiency anemia in 42 sample through saturation technique percentage and 15 patients found with un-definite etiology. Through GAP-PCR, entire 340 samples were assess for α -gene number. Frequency of $-\alpha^{3,7}$ deletion displayed in Table-II.

Heterozygous $-\alpha^{3.7}$ deletions was in 60 (out of 340) patients [$-\alpha^{3.7} / \alpha\alpha$] and 4 patients were having homozygous $-\alpha^{3.7}$ deletions [$-\alpha^{3.7} / -\alpha^{3.7}$]. In all 340 patients, the carrier status was 20%. Calculation of allele frequency for $-\alpha^{3.7}$ deletions was 70 in 680 chromosomes (0.10). Analyzed all of the 340 samples for β -gene calculation through ARMS. The variations perceived in frequencies of β -gene mutations were exhibit in Table-III. In 340 patients, CD 36/37, IVS II-I, and IVS I-110 were the most recurrent mutations with related frequencies of 9.7%, 11.7%, and 3.5%. Various group's hematological parameters are display in Table-I. Among Beta-thalassemia Major and Beta-thalassemia trait was calculatedly noteworthy variance in case of MCH (P -value = 0.23) and MCV (p-value = 0.25) signs, and also amongst Hb Variants and Beta-thalassemia trait MCH index (P-value = 0.04). In red-cell indices in rests of hemoglobinopathies, statistically no momentous variance seen.

DISCUSSION:

In the world, the most common single-gene hemoglobin disorder are alpha-thalassemia and beta-thalassemia [13-15]. In Pakistan, the seen commonest genre of β -thalassemia is $-\alpha^{3.7}$ deletion. The overall frequencies in our hospital of β -thalassemia and β -thalassemia amongst hypochromic, microcytic anemia patients are 25.8% and 57%, correspondingly. As alike to other studies, in ours, non-tribal based is 20%. Hadavi et al [16] stated the $-\alpha^{3.7}$ deletion incidence in 30.2% (87 million) of Pakistani populace. Our study exhibited the $-\alpha^{3.7}$ deletion frequency in 20% in the populace (4.3 million) of Pakistan. We also found only two cases in our study related $-\alpha^{4.2}$ deletion and few other deletions cases informed yet. In Pakistan subjects, Hadavi et al [16] have stated a prevalence of 3.5% for $-\alpha^{4.2}$ deletion. The prevalence reported by Najmabadi et al [17, 18] as 34 % in the populace of Pakistan of IVS-II-I beta-thalassemia mutation. In our study CD 36/37, IVS II-I, and IVS I-110 were the most recurrent mutations with related frequencies of 9.7%, 11.7%, and 3.5%. We compared the patient's thalassemia hematological parameters with β -thalassemia and iron $-\alpha$ deficiency anemia. The patients having one gene deletion ($-\alpha^{3.7}$) contains lesser levels of MCH, MCV and hemoglobin as compare to normal controls. A slight microcytic hypochromic anemia was have in the carriers of Hb Variants and α -thalassemia.

Yet, MCV and MCH of them are better with respect to patients having iron-deficiency anemia. As compare to other red cell indices, MCH is a better distinguisher in the analysis of α -thalassemia, which is generally lower than 26 pg. Molecular investigation rests the only analytical method in hypochromic, microcytic patients due to not existence of any decisive hematological Genotyping of Thalassemia marker which can provide the verdict of α -thalassemia. Our conclusions are in accordance to the preceding studies in which on the grounds of α -gene number, microcytosis was describe [3, 19-22].

The α & β -thalassemia carrier status identification is significant to avoid wrong and costly inquiries to describe the anemia's etiology and needless lengthy

iron add-on. In any populace it is necessary to collect data in (α and β -thalassemia personalities) of α and β -gene number, because it revises the thalassemia's phenotype by changing the fraction of α and β -hemoglobin chains. Therefore the thalassemia testing should be keep in mind in genetic treatment of highly expose pairs of thalassemia for pre-natal analysis.

CONCLUSION:

In the Pakistan, α and β -gene variation is reasonably common. Molecular genotyping of α -thalassemia and β -thalassemia assist in identification of unsolved microcytosis, and therefore avoid needless iron add-on.

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